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Evaluation 2 of "Economic vs. Epidemiological Approaches to Measuring the Human Capital Impacts of Infectious Disease Elimination"

Evaluator 2 (Unjournal, anonymous)

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Referee report prepared for the Unjournal on "Economic vs. Epidemiological Approaches to Measuring the Human Capital Impacts of Infectious Disease Elimination" This well-written paper provides an interesting comparison of two different approaches to estimating the long-term health, education and income impacts of measles in the United States. Both approaches center around using variation in measles exposure generated by the rollout of the measles vaccine in 1963. The first approach is epidemiology-based, using state-year data on measles infections along with vaccination rates to estimate the share-ever-infected of each cohort and then using this as the independent variable of interest. The second approach, which the authors rightly identify as the main approach within the economics literature, uses variation in pre-vaccine measles severity, proxied by measles mortality, interacted with a dummy for the prevaccination period, as the key independent variable. Note that, following the authors, I will refer to this second approach as the reduced form approach. When using the reduced form approach, the authors find significant long-term impacts of measles in the expected ways: exposure to a higher measles mortality environment was associated with lower levels of high school completion, lower income, higher levels of unemployment and higher levels of welfare income and food stamp usage. The epidemiological approach finds noticeably different impacts, with higher shares of measles infection showing a statistically insignificant relationship with later life outcomes. Additionally, these estimates appear far more sensitive to model specification than the reduced form results. The paper presents compelling evidence that epidemiological and reduced form approaches provide different perspectives on the long-term impacts of infectious disease elimination. However, to properly interpret those differences, I think the paper needs to dig a bit deeper into the impacts of the different assumptions built into the two approaches and offer more guidance as to how to interpret differences in the results. I elaborate on these points in the comments below. 1) One significant focus of the paper when interpreting results, and in my view one of the significant theoretical differences between taking epidemiological versus reduced form approaches, is the difference between focusing on cases versus deaths. It is understandable that most reduced form studies will inevitably rely on mortality statistics because the data are more readily available and more accurately measured. The underlying assumption of most of these reduced form papers is that a worse disease environment in terms of mortality is likely highly correlated with a worse disease environment for those who survive. The paper would benefit from offering the reader more guidance about how likely this assumption is to hold both in terms of measles and more broadly. Figure 4 (a really helpful figure for understanding the three different measures of measles exposure) suggests that infection rates and mortality rates do not necessarily move in lockstep with one another. Note how Washington and Arkansas completely flip in terms of level of measles exposure when switching from share infected to pre-vaccine mortality. The reader needs more context for how a deadly outbreak of measles differs from a less lethal outbreak and how those differences likely translate into different patterns of human capital formation. This seems essential to both understanding the empirical results but also to understanding the value of the two different approaches to measurement and when we should favor one over the other. 2) While the point above is primarily about the real-world aspects of more and less lethal measles outbreaks, the empirical results also make me wonder if there is a very different but important issue related to

the econometrics of the epidemiological model versus the reduced form model. I think both models and their assumptions are both well motivated and well explained in the current manuscript. However, the main results suggest that there is something missing on the econometrics side. In particular, it was surprising to see how sensitive the epidemiological estimates were to the choice of controlling for either cohort trends or cohort fixed effects. The reduced form results were pretty much unchanged by this choice but the epidemiological results not only changed substantially but typically flipped signs. This is noted in the paper but never explained. In my view, it is essential to figure out what is going on here. What I suspect is that the method for calculating cohort exposure to measles by estimating the number of susceptible individuals in the cohort each successive year is generating a correlation by construction with the cohort trends that might be throwing off results through multicollinearity issues. I haven't thought that through fully but I think the paper needs to grapple with whether the inclusion of cohort trends is compatible with the way cohort exposure is calculated. While the econometrics of that remain a bit out of reach for me, it is far clearer to me that the cohort fixed effects results are both easier to interpret and see more defensible. That being the case, the paper needs to do more to explain the opposite signs on the long-term effects results for the epidemiological results compared to the reduced form results. All of the reasoning throughout the paper relates to different magnitudes of effects, not different signs. Coming up with an explanation for those sign flips is important for establishing the credibility of the epidemiological approach (note that the power of the approach to predict future outbreaks is really convincing evidence of the credibility of the approach, evidence that I think could be emphasized even more, but explaining the sign flips still seems essential as well). The only explanation for sign flips between infections and deaths that immediately comes to mind is if there is some sort of culling effect going on, leaving a healthier but smaller population in the wake of severe measles outbreaks. 3) There were a few places where I would like to see a bit more about measurement issues for both measures and whether those issues are likely to generate attenuation biases in the results. For the reduced form approach, how accurately does stated cause of death capture measles deaths? Are deaths from related complications like pneumonia included? If not, do we have a sense of how much measles deaths are being underreported? If so, do we have a sense of how much they might be overreported? For the epidemiological approach, could you offer a bit more to get a handle on the variation in both reporting rates and immunization rates? For the reporting rates, I find the approach of allowing them to vary over time the most reasonable and would recommend that it be the main approach rather than relegated to the appendix. I'd also be curious as to how variation in reporting rates correlates with other relevant state statistics (from the map, it appears that higher reporting rates are potentially positively correlated with income and with school attendance, pretty relevant correlations). For the immunization rates, I understand the need to use national estimates given the lack of state-level data but we know that in recent years these rates vary substantially across states. From the October 18, 2019 Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report, the national average for MMR vaccination rate is 94.7% yet some states like some states like Idaho are below 90%. That would lead to some substantial measurement error in the measles exposure estimates. It would be useful to track down earlier data on variation in immunization rates across states or to at least point to sources that document a divergence in immunization rates being a more modern phenomenon. 4) While this paper

highlights the differences in measuring infection versus mortality by comparing the epidemiological model results to the reduced form results, and does so with solid discussions, it seems equally important to dive deeper into the differences in the reduced form results in this paper and those in Atwood (2022). As noted in this paper, the Atwood results aren't exactly the same as they focus on measles cases rather than deaths. Given this, should we expect the Atwood (2022) results to more closely track the epidemiological results of this paper? Or is it really the methodology (epi versus reduced form) that makes the biggest difference as opposed to the cases versus mortality, meaning the Atwood results should more closely align with this paper's reduced form results? Doing more to address these questions would both help distinguish this paper's contribution from Atwood (2022) but also provide a lot more clarity about the broad goal of showing how measurement of infectious disease impacts estimates of its long-term impacts